

ISic0002

Epitaph for Lurius Zosimus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas,

inventory 3502

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) · M(anibus) · s(acrum)

2. Lurius · Zosimus

3. vix(it) · annis · VII

4. Luria · Melanth(e) i

5. n · suo · filio · fecit

Apparatus

Mommsen rejects the alternative reading of 'Melanthin(a) suo'

Translation (en)

Sacred to the shades of the underworld. Luris Zosimus lived for 7 years. Luria Melanthe made it for her son.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491568

EDR 141180

EDCS 21900397

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7075 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 2

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